

IMPLEMENTATION OF A HYBRID ENERGY SYSTEM COMBINING RES AND H₂ IN AN OFFICE BUILDING IN LAVRION GREECE

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Abstract

More than 40% of the total energy consumed in the EU is used to cover the needs for heating, cooling and electricity of buildings. As the major part of this energy is produced from combustion of oil and natural gas, the Building Sector is a major contributor to Green-House Gas (GHG) emissions. To contribute to the realisation of the objectives set by the EC for the reduction of GHG emissions and the increase of the share of renewable energy, the trend for the Building Sector is to move from fossil fuels based energy production to the use of renewable energy sources (RES) and clean fuels to produce the required energy to cover the building energy needs. However, in order to ensure continuous operation of energy systems based on RES it is necessary to find a proper way to balance the intermittent nature of RES. In this scope, hydrogen (H₂) is examined as the most appropriate energy storage medium, mainly due to its high energy density by mass and the fact that when burnt the only by-product is water.

In this frame, this paper presents a new concept for the development of an intelligent, self-sustained and zero CO₂ emission hybrid energy system to cover electric power, heating and cooling loads (tri-generation) of either residential/commercial buildings or districts of buildings. In the presented system, the primary energy is harvested from RES and is directly used to cover contingent loads, while the excess energy is converted to H₂ to be used as energy storage material and to be further applied as a green fuel to cover the building heating needs through direct combustion or to produce combined heating and electricity by means of fuel cells.

A prototype system has already been installed in a ≈500 m² office building at the Lavrion Technological and Cultural Park of NTUA, Greece, and is currently in operation. The system design and construction considerations are described in the paper together with monitored data from the system and the building operation. A preliminary evaluation of the system performance based on actual measurements has shown that the application of such a system to cover the energy needs of buildings is feasible.

INTRODUCTION

More than 40% of the total energy consumed in the EU is used to cover the needs for heating, cooling and electricity of buildings (ECOFYS, 2004). As the major part of this energy is produced from combustion of fossil fuels, the Building Sector is a major contributor to Green-House Gas (GHG) emissions. Given the fact that EC has set the objectives to reduce GHG emissions by 20% until year 2020 and to increase the share of renewable energy, there is a trend for the Building Sector to move from fossil fuels based energy production to the use of renewable energy sources (RES) and clean fuels energy production to cover the building energy needs. In this frame, hydrogen (H₂) is examined as the most appropriate energy storage medium, mainly due to its high energy density by mass and the fact that when burnt the only by-product is water.

A detailed review of the related literature showed that there is already a number of case studies where H₂ technologies are employed in buildings.

In the frame of RES2H2 project (RES2H2, 2002 – 2007), two test sites were developed in Greece and Canary islands respectively. The Greek site employed a system composed of a 25 kW water electrolyser, metal hydride tanks filled with a LaNi5-type alloy and a H₂ compressor for the filling of storage cylinders, all powered by a 500 kW synchronous wind turbine. The Canary islands site included an alkaline electrolyser, six PEM fuel cells, a H₂ storage tank and a desalination system to produce drinking water through reverse osmosis, all powered by a 225kW wind turbine.

A combined wind-H₂ system was also installed in Utsira, Norway. In this pilot project, 10 households were supplied exclusively by the energy generated from two 600 kW wind turbines. The excess energy was converted to H₂ through a 48 kW electrolysis unit paired with a 55 kW H₂ combustion engine and a 10 kW fuel cell.

The Hydrogen Office building is another example of a building powered by a system combining renewable sources and H₂. The system includes a 750kW wind turbine, 30kW electrolyser, 10kW hydrogen fuel cell and a geothermal source heat pump. The project was based on the results of PURE (Promoting Unst Renewable Energy) project.

A demonstration plant combining solar energy with H₂ has been designed and installed at the central library building of the Research Centre Julich with the aim to render the building completely autonomous. The total installed capacity is 38 kW_e and the major components of the plant are PV cells (nominal peak power output of 43 kW_p), 110 lead batteries with a capacity of 304 kWh, a 26 kW electrolyser, a storage system consisting of 18 pressure bottles containing compressed H₂ at 120 bar, and an alkaline fuel cell system with 6.5 kW power output (Schucan, 2000).

The aim of the PVFSYS project was also to develop a PV and H₂-based system for storing solar energy by means of H₂. The system aimed to avoid using batteries, thus fuel cells were the only means to provide electricity when the load exceeded the PV production. A small battery was used for the safe shut-down of equipment in case of emergency. Two systems were built, one in Sophia Antipolis defined as a test bench and a pilot plant located in Agrate. The main difference between the two systems was the fact that in the test bench, oxygen was stored and used in the fuel cell, increasing efficiency.

The Hydrogen and Renewables Integration (HARI) project goal is to demonstrate and gain experience in the integration of H₂ energy storage with renewable energy systems (Gammon et al., 2006). The demonstration system is located at Leicestershire, UK and includes two 13 kW_p wind turbines, an additional 13 kW_p of photovoltaics, two micro-hydroelectric turbines with a combined output of 3 kW, a 36 kW electrolyser, two fuel cells (2 kW and 5 kW respectively) and pressurized H₂ storage cylinders with a capacity of 2856 Nm³ at 137 bar.

A more detailed review of H₂ production systems powered by renewable energy sources can also be found in Lymberopoulos, 2005. A more general review of various stationary H₂ energy demonstration systems can also be found in Ulleberg et al., 2007.

This paper presents a new concept for the development of an intelligent, self-sustained and zero CO₂ emission hybrid energy system to cover electric power, heating and cooling loads (tri-generation) of either residential/commercial buildings or districts of buildings. In the presented system, the primary energy harvested from RES is directly used to cover contingent loads, while the excess energy is converted to H₂ to be used as energy storage material and to be further applied as a green fuel to cover the building heating needs through direct combustion or to produce combined heating and electricity by means of fuel cells. The system design and construction considerations are described together with monitored data from the system and the building operation.

INSTALLATION SITE AND DEMONSTRATION BUILDING CHARACTERISTICS

The RES-H₂ hybrid energy system is installed in a demonstration building within the Lavrion Technological and Cultural Park (LTCP), which is located in the city of Lavrion, in the South-Eastern Attica region, approximately 50 km from Athens, Greece. The LTCP covers a total area of 250,000 m² and includes 41 buildings with a total floor space of 25,000 m².

The choice of the specific area for the installation of the RES-H₂ system was mainly based on the particular characteristics of the LTCP, such as:

- The area is exposed to favorable meteorological conditions all over the year, making it a very good candidate for the installation of RES systems based on solar and wind energy. Specifically, meteorological data gathered from a weather station installed inside the LTCP for years 2007 and 2008, show that the average solar radiation was 1597 kWh/m² and 1657 kWh/m² and the average wind speed was 5.63 m/sec and 5.89 m/sec, respectively for these years.
- The variety of available buildings in the LTCP, which facilitated the selection of the most appropriate one. Some of the criteria that were taken into consideration were the building use, its total surface area, ability to integrate the required equipment in it, etc.
- The LTCP, due to its nature, attracts high technology and cultural activities and is often visited by companies, educational institutions and scientific community experts. This kind of interest is expected to promote the dissemination of the developed RES-H₂ system and raise public awareness.

The overall dimensions of the selected building are 30.50 m x 15.50 m, with a maximum height of approximately 8.35 m. The building has a ground floor with a surface area of approximately 375 m² and an attic floor with an area of 150 m² (total surface area approximately 525 m²). In Figure 1, a 3D interior view of the building is shown.

Fig. 1. 3D view of the demonstration building interior.

The building envelope consists of a concrete structure with double brick walls and non-insulated single-glazed windows. The roof consists of metallic panels with 1" polyurethane insulation layer in the middle. An exterior view of the building is presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Exterior view of the demonstration building at its present state.

HYBRID ENERGY SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The philosophy of the developed hybrid energy system is to use RES to harvest primary energy to be directly used to cover the building energy loads. When the production from RES is greater than the total building consumption, the excess energy is stored in the form of H_2 , which is produced from water by electrolysis. On the other hand, when the production from RES is less than the total building consumption, the stored H_2 is applied as a green fuel to cover the building electric and thermal energy demand, through combined heat and power generation by means of a fuel cell.

Consequently, the hybrid energy system basic components are (Figure 3):

- The RES, namely photovoltaic panels (46.8 kW total installed power) to exploit solar power and wind turbines (36 kW total installed power) to exploit wind power.
- A water electrolysis unit (22.3 kW) to produce the gaseous H_2 .
- H_2 distribution grid and H_2 storage vessels (3480 lt max water capacity).
- A compressor to enable the H_2 storage in high pressure vessels (up to 200 bar).
- A fuel cell (5.8 kW for small-scale and 20 kW for large-scale phases respectively) to convert the stored H_2 to electrical and thermal energy.
- An H_2 burner to produce thermal energy.

The system also includes an advanced safety system comprising different types of detectors as well as an Energy Management and Control System (EMCS) to control the flow of energy and the operation of all the units of the system. It must be noted that remote monitoring and control are also possible.

Comparing the developed system to the ones presented in the review analysis, several differences can be identified. Firstly, most of these systems rely on relatively large total installed power from RES (in the order of several hundred kW), which can be unrealistic from both an economical and construction point of view for

domestic building applications. Secondly, as shown in Figure 1, the proposed system can be completely integrated in a medium sized building and with the exception of the RES, it does not require large-scale exterior installations. Lastly, the hybrid energy system includes prototype components, such as the H₂ burner for producing thermal energy that have not been used so far in similar applications.

For the dimensioning of the system, simulations of the building energy needs were carried out using TRNSYS and meteorological data of the selected area. Consequently, based on the simulations' results, a rough initial estimation for each component was made. In any case, the data that are going to be collected during the system's operation will help to develop a more accurate dimensioning procedure for future installations.

The installation and implementation of the entire system is carried out in 2 phases, the small-scale and large-scale, respectively. The aim of the small-scale phase is the installation of the various sub-components of the system and the verification of their synergistic operation. During this phase, only a part of the building energy needs, corresponding to the attic floor, will be covered. In the large-scale, some additional sub-components (20kW fuel cell, H₂ compressor and H₂ burner) will be installed, while the system will cover the energy needs of the entire building. During this phase, optimization of the system will be carried out.

Fig. 3. Conceptual diagram of the RES-H₂ hybrid energy production and consumption system.

DESIGN REQUIREMENTS, SPECIFICATIONS AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SYSTEM

The whole design process was divided in three actions that were carried out in parallel:

- The design of the hybrid energy system itself, meaning selecting the various subsystems and components, accounting for the expected interactions during their synergistic operation and conceptualizing the management system.
- The design and modifications in the building available space and investigation of different arrangement scenarios for the integration of the equipment.
- The review of all the relevant safety directives and specifications in order to identify the requirements and constraints that should be followed during the installation and operation of the system.

In the following sections an overview of each of the above actions is presented.

RES installation

The RES park (Figure 4) is located near the demonstration building (85 m maximum distance) and includes:

- 6 downwind three-bladed turbines of 6 kW capacity each.
- 624 photovoltaic panels of thin film technology with 46.8 kWp nominal power.

Fig. 4. RES park placement.

Photovoltaic panels

The selected photovoltaic cells are based on thin film technology, made of Copper Indium Gallium Diselenide (CIGS) absorbers, with an efficiency ratio of 9.9 %. The main advantages of CIGS in comparison to other technologies are (Powalla et al, 2004):

- Thin film photovoltaic cells exhibit less voltage drop than traditional panels in relation to increased temperatures.
- Thin film photovoltaic cells have higher energy production in low-light and shading conditions.

The panels are installed on the roof of a nearby building, facing South with an inclination of approximately 23°. The total panel area is 475 m² and the expected annual energy production is about 80000 kWh.

The panels are divided in 6 main circuits powering 6 inverters, which are connected in pairs. The efficiency of the inverters is close to 98%. The system is equipped with power balancers, which enable a circuit connection of the inverters to a 3-phase low-voltage grid of the building controlled by appropriate power balancing system.

Wind turbines

The selected wind turbines are based on downwind technology and are equipped with a flexible blade system connected to permanent magnet generator that enables the wind turbine to generate power in light as well as in strong winds (cut-in speed: 2.5 m/s). The blades (5.5 m in diameter) are held by springs that allow them to pitch and cone in high wind speeds in order to reduce the induced stresses. The turbine frame also includes a service brake that acts on the rotor shaft and is used for maintenance purposes.

The mast (9 m height) that is connected to the turbine frame has a steel base plate that incorporates a raising and lowering mechanism. The top of the mast has a yaw bearing assembly that permits the rotation of the turbine frame. The rotor is therefore able to turn 360° and self orientate, depending on wind direction and speed. The expected annual energy production is about 50000 kWh.

Hydrogen production by water electrolysis

In order to produce the necessary gaseous H₂ for the hybrid energy system a water electrolysis unit (electrolyser) is used. The selected unit is a commercially available electrolyser (model G6HP) developed by Erre Due srl. The HP variant means that H₂ is produced at 12 bar instead of 2.5 bar of the standard version. The main technical characteristics of the electrolyser are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Installed electrolyser technical characteristics.

Description	Unit	Value
Rated production capacity (dry gas basis): H ₂ (stored)	Nm ³ /h	4.0
H ₂ outlet pressure	Bar	12
H ₂ purity: with DXH6 purifier (std)	%vol	>99.999 (99.3 – 99.8)
Operating environment temperature	°C	+5 to +35
Power supply	22.3 kW 3 Phase 400 VAC	

The electrolyser is also equipped with a Scada system in order to be able to communicate with a PC through Ethernet connection. The H₂ production subsystem is completed by a purifier that increases the produced H₂ purity so as to meet the specifications of the fuel cell.

Hydrogen distribution grid and hydrogen storage

The H₂ distribution grid (Figure 5) takes H₂ from the point of production, i.e. the electrolyser, to the storage section and subsequently brings H₂ from the storage vessels to the fuel cell as well as to the H₂ burner.

The required information for the design of the H₂ grid is mainly the flow, temperature, pressure and composition of H₂. The piping used is made of stainless steel 316. The distribution grid consists of two sections relative to the pressure. The first section, where the H₂ is found at 12 bar as produced by the electrolyser, is located between the electrolyser and the H₂ compressor. The rest of the grid can reach a working pressure of 200 bar if needed. Before each point of use, pressure regulators are used to adjust the pressure according to specific equipment requirements. Obviously, check valves, relief valves etc. are included in the distribution grid. Special attention must be given to the presence of 3 electromagnetic valves that are controlled by the safety system and can be closed in the case of an alarm, effectively isolating different sections of the distribution grid and cutting the flow of H₂.

Fig. 5. Section of the H₂ distribution grid, H₂ storage bundle (1 of 4) and P&I diagram.

Concerning the storage, in theory, H₂ can be stored in any of the 3 states; gas, liquid, or solid. However, for all 3 possibilities there are still a lot of challenges, resulting in various H₂ storage technologies either on the market or in research environments. At present, the most appropriate choice for the targeted application is in compressed gaseous state inside pressure vessels. The reasons being that this is currently being tested and used in a multitude of applications and it is the most evolved of the available technologies, thus ensuring increased reliability. At the same time, it is the most economic among the existing technological solutions.

For the needs of the project, Type I vessels have been used. Specifically, 4 bundles of cylinders have been installed with 12 vessels each (Figure 5). There are a total of 36 vessels of 80 lt water capacity and 12 vessels of 50 lt water capacity (max water capacity is 3480 lt). Maximum working pressure is set at 200 bar, therefore the maximum stored volume of H₂ is approximately 690 Nm³ (or equivalently approximately 62 kg of H₂).

Fuel cell

For the purposes of the project, two Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) fuel cell prototypes were going to be developed and installed in the demonstration building. The first fuel cell (Figure 6) capable of delivering 5,8 kW of electrical power at nominal continuous power conditions will be used for the small-scale installation. The second fuel cell, capable of delivering 20 kW of electrical power, will be installed during the second phase of the project.

Since the fuel cell produces DC current, an inverter is needed in order to convert it to AC and connect it to the rest of the building's power grid. In the case of the small-scale fuel cell, an external inverter has been used (DELTA DHF-1AC-5000W). This inverter has a 51 V nominal DC input and a maximum DC power rating of 6 kW. Table 2 describes the technical characteristics of the small scale fuel cell.

Table 2. PEM fuel cell (small-scale) technical characteristics.

Description	Unit	Value
Nominal continuous electrical power	kW	5.8
Voltage	V _{DC}	31-72 not regulated
System efficiency at nominal continuous power	%	>40
Inlet pressure	bara	2-5
Fuel Consumption	Nm ³ /h	4.3 @ nominal continuous power

Fig. 6. Installed PEM fuel cell (small-scale).

Safety directives and regulations – Implementation

The acceptance of H₂ as an energy storage medium is not homogeneous within the different member states of Europe. At the current state, the final specifications are decided by the opinions of the relevant national bodies.

As gaseous H₂ constitutes a potential explosion danger, there are two specific European legislations that contain the minimum requirements to be met for the safe use of H₂: the ATEX directives (1), regarding gases and explosive atmospheres, and the Pressure Equipment Directive (PED) (2).

1. ATEX is the name commonly given to the framework for controlling explosive atmospheres arising from gases, vapours, mists or dusts, and the standards for equipment and protective systems used in them. It is based on the requirements of two European Directives: 94/9/EC – ATEX Product Directive (also known as ATEX 95, ATEX 100, ATEX 100a) and 99/92/EC – ATEX User Directive (also known as ATEX 118, ATEX 137).
2. For fixed H₂ installations the equipment used with gas or liquid under pressure is regulated by the PED (97/23/EC) that applies to the design, manufacture and conformity assessment of pressure equipment and assemblies with maximum allowable pressure PS greater than 0.5 bar. The term “Pressure equipment” includes vessels, piping, safety accessories and pressure accessories.

Also, some of the more detailed directives come from the National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) standards. Specifically, standards NFPA 50A and NFPA 50B have been superseded by NFPA 55 (NFPA 55, Edition 2010) that applies to requirements for designing H₂ systems including container locations, safety devices, marking, piping, venting, and other components.

Finally, the European Industrial Gases Association (EIGA) code of practice is considered to reflect the best practices for the guidance of designers and operators of gaseous H₂ stations (EIGA, 2006).

Other regulations and codes that can be taken into consideration when designing H₂ based systems are:

- ISO-22734_1:2008, which covers the safety issues related to generators using the water electrolysis process for industrial and commercial applications.
- IEC 62282, a 6-part fuel cell standard that deals with stationary, portable, and micro fuel cell power systems.

When seeking to control the risks associated with the use of H₂, it is important firstly to take all reasonable steps to prevent H₂ leakage, secondly to ensure that if there is a leak a flammable atmosphere cannot accumulate, thirdly to control potential ignition sources where flammable atmospheres may accumulate, and finally, to use suitable protection against the fire and explosion hazards.

The basic principle to evaluate the location where each equipment should be installed is to respect the safety distance. The safety distance is the minimum distance between a hazard source and an object (human, equipment or environment), which will mitigate the effect of a likely foreseeable incident and prevent a minor incident from escalating into a larger incident.

The safety aspect has received a great deal of attention in order to ensure that all relevant regulations and recommended practises are followed. During the design process, safety issues were divided in 2 groups of

interventions. The first is related to the way that the equipment is arranged in specific areas of the demonstration building and the second to the installation of an advanced safety system.

Equipment arrangement

An isolated area, named the H₂ GenConsStor area, made of concrete frame and double brick walls (60 min fire resistant) was constructed inside the building to host the electrolyser, fuel cell and H₂ burner (Figure 7). There are 2 entrances to this area sealed by 60 min fire resistant doors. Each equipment is placed in a separate room with dimensions 5m x 5m x 5m in a way that leaves an open corridor serving as an escape route towards either exit, in case of alarm. A dedicated ventilation system ensures continuous air replenishment inside each room during equipment operation, with fresh air being sucked 15m away from the engine room. All the electrical installations in the area meet the requirements of relevant ATEX directives, while the electrolyser room also has a relief wall.

The H₂ distribution grid and storage area are placed outside the building. The piping is mounted on the external building wall, while the H₂ stacks are placed on a concrete base and under a protective roof to avoid direct exposure to sunlight and rain.

Safety system

The safety system that has been installed in the H₂ GenConsStor area uses various types of detectors to monitor different events (Figure 7). Specifically, the following components have been installed:

- H₂ detectors to check for increased H₂ levels, indicating leakage of H₂.
- Infrared flame detectors to check for fire fuelled by H₂, since this kind of fire can only be detected by the produced heat.
- Smoke detectors to check for fire caused by other means.
- Contact switches on the H₂ GenConsStor area entrances.
- Local control panels next to the H₂ GenConsStor area entrances.
- Electromagnetic valves in different sections of the H₂ distribution grid.
- In addition to the sensors installed inside the H₂ GenConsStor area, heat sensors are also installed in the to monitor ambient temperature.
- Cooling water lines to be used in case of increased ambient temperature in order to control the H₂ stacks temperature.
- An inert gas (N₂) extinguishing system that floods the H₂ GenConsStor area in case of a severe alarm.
- Audiovisual alarms.

Fig. 7. Plan of detectors installed in the H₂ GenConsStor area.

All of the above are connected to a central automated monitoring and control unit. Specific series of procedures are foreseen according to the type of alarm. The system can automatically send notifications via e-mail and SMS and can also be operated remotely.

Monitoring system and monitored data

In order to analyze the flow of energy among the various equipment, a monitoring system has been installed in the demonstration building. This system can measure and store in real-time the energy produced by the RES or the fuel cell and the energy consumed by the equipment and the building. This is accomplished using smart metering devices installed in the building main electrical board that measure electrical signals. These devices also offer advanced functionalities such as alarming, trending, forecasting, and other. The architecture of the monitoring system is displayed in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Architecture of the monitoring system.

To facilitate the optimum use of the available energy, the building consumptions were grouped depending on their type as well as on their location. For each monitored parameter several magnitudes are recorded including power (real, reactive, apparent), energy (real, reactive, apparent), demand, power factor etc. The list of monitored supplies is as follows:

- Main connection to the grid
- Renewable Energy Sources (separately for photovoltaic panels and wind turbines)
- Fuel Cell
- Burner
- Electrolyser
- Total electrical consumption of lighting
- Total electrical consumption of the air condition and air heating units
- Total electrical consumption of power sockets according to each building room

The data gathered from the monitoring system are fed to a Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition System (SCADA) implemented on a separate PC. Both the monitoring system and SCADA communicate with a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) that manages the operation of each component. The exchange of information between system components and the PLC is done using a common BUS and common protocol (Modbus TCP/IP). The philosophy of operation is based on the energy exchange balance between the RES and the building consumptions (State of Charge – SOC) and is described in an abstract level in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Control algorithm philosophy.

PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION PROFILES

The preliminary data presented here are gathered from the small-scale phase, i.e. from the operation of the attic floor. The goal is to examine the production of energy by the RES and the consumption of energy by the building. In order to standardize the latter, a typical scenario was implemented for the building use, with the applied rules being:

- Lights turn on at 08:00 and turn off at 18:00
- HVAC turns on at approximately 09:00 and turns off at approximately 17:00
- Inside temperature setpoint is at 21 degrees Celsius
- All consumptions are off during Saturdays and Sundays

This scenario was deemed suitable for an office building situated in Greece during the winter. In any case, it is possible to define different usage scenarios according to preference and/or geographic location to examine a variety of combinations.

Sample measurements for a 24h period are presented below. The selected day is the 11th of March 2011, a day with no clouds, an average solar radiation of 181 W/m², an average wind speed of 1.2 m/sec and an average temperature of 8.7 degrees Celsius. Due to these meteorological conditions, this day is representative of medium to high RES production, expecting high photovoltaic and very low energy production from the wind turbines. At the same time, building consumption is expected to be average due to the relatively low temperature.

The data represent the energy production profiles from the RES and the energy consumption profiles from the most important loads of the demonstration building.

The production profiles for the photovoltaic panels and the wind turbines are given in Figures 10a and 10b, respectively.

Fig. 10a. (left) and 10b (right). RES production profiles.

As can be seen, photovoltaic production is very good and consistent with the daily variation of the solar radiance. The absence of clouds results in an ideal bell-shaped production curve. At the same time, wind turbine production is extremely low due to the low wind speeds experienced during the selected period.

The consumption of the building attic floor is presented in Figures 11a and 11b for two different types of loads (lighting and HVAC respectively).

Fig. 11a. (left) and 11b (right). Consumption profiles by type of load.

CONCLUSIONS

A Hybrid Energy System has been successfully designed, installed and is currently operating in a medium sized building at the Lavrion Technological and Cultural Park, Attika, Greece, aiming to verify the system efficiency and reliability. The system comprises a water electrolyser, H₂ compressor, pressurized H₂ storage cylinders and fuel cell. The overall system is powered by a small RES park and controlled by an intelligent algorithm that manages the flow of energy, operation and control of the equipment, in order to assure continuous building operation. The prototype system is continuously monitored to evaluate its performance against process efficiency, collaboration with RES and grid. Synergy between its various components as well as functionality of the automation and control and fulfillment of the safety standards are also evaluated. Significant experience has been gained, giving valuable insight for system upgrade, where a H₂ compressor, a new fuel cell of higher capacity and a prototype H₂ burner will be integrated to the system. Apart from the technical parameters to be tested and monitored in the scaled up system, data related to the installation and operation cost, maintenance rate and lifetime of the various parts of the system will be collected. The outcome of the evaluated results will be implemented to a detailed feasibility study and economic assessment of the proposed Hybrid system.

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